

1 **Soil organic carbon and nutrient content across agricultural systems in the forest-savannah**
2 **transition zone of Cameroon**

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22

23 **Abstract**

24 Accurate knowledge of soil characteristics is indispensable for large-scale agriculture while
25 ensuring sustainability, climate change adaptation, and mitigation, which is lacking in Cameroon.
26 This study aimed to assess soil organic carbon (SOC) and nutrient (NPK) content across
27 agricultural systems in the forest-savannah transition zone of Cameroon. Seven agricultural
28 systems were identified namely: the forest-based cocoa agroforestry (F_{cocoa}), savannah-based
29 cocoa agroforestry (S_{cocoa}), transition zone-based cocoa agroforestry (T_{cocoa}), savannah mixed
30 cropping of yam, pumpkin, and maize (S_{ypm}), savannah mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava and
31 maize (S_{gcm}), transition zone mixed cropping of yam, pumpkin, and maize (T_{ypm}), and the transition
32 zone mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava, and maize (T_{gcm}). The soil was sampled at two depths,
33 0 -10 cm (upper layer) and 10 -30 cm (lower layer) in three replicates for each farming system
34 and analyzed. Significant differences appeared in soil organic carbon (SOC) ($p < 0.002$), Total
35 nitrogen (N) ($p < 0.001$), C:N ratio ($p < 0.002$), pH ($p < 0.01$), bulk density (Bd) ($p < 0.03$), soil
36 organic carbon stock (SOCS) ($p < 0.001$), and soil nitrogen stock (SNS) ($p < 0.001$). In the upper
37 and lower layers, the highest concentrations of SOC (25.0 and 16.6 g kg⁻¹), N (2.3 and 1.5 g kg⁻¹),
38 and P (5.1 and 3.3g kg⁻¹) were recorded in F_{cocoa} , and K (176.9 and 129.3 mg kg⁻¹) in S_{cocoa}
39 respectively. In the croplands, soil nutrient content was higher in the transition zone while
40 savannah croplands showed higher Bd (≥ 1.4 g cm⁻³). Soil nutrient content decreased from upper
41 to lower soil layers with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the croplands for pH, SOCS, and
42 SNS, with a higher magnitude ($p < 0.01$) in S_{gcm} . Thus, agroforestry can be considered a potential
43 solution towards ecological resilience.

44 **Keywords:** cocoa agroforestry, annual croplands, soil carbon, soil nutrients, forest-savannah
45 transition

46 1. Introduction

47 Soil and its potential as a managed sink for atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) is a topic of great
48 interest lately (Wang et al., 2016; Chu et al., 2018). Soil is the major carbon (C) pool in the global
49 terrestrial ecosystem (Lal, 2003; Scharlemann et al., 2014), with about 75% of the C stored on land
50 (Guo and Gifford, 2002; Scharlemann et al., 2014). Therefore, soil plays a fundamental role in
51 climate change adaptation and mitigation (Mirzaee et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2016; Chu et al.,
52 2018), and it is the most important component in sustainable land management (Scholes and Van,
53 1997). Soil C has positive effects on the physical (bulk density, structure, stability, porosity),
54 chemical (exchangeable cations, CEC, pH), and biological (energy substrate for soil fauna and
55 microflora) properties of the soil (Feller et al., 2001). It is the main component of soil organic
56 matter (SOM) (Tsozué et al., 2019). SOM interacts with microorganisms through biological
57 processes leading to the bio-cycling of soil nutrients (C, N, P, and K) for plants' benefit (Huang et
58 al., 2005; Wibowo and Kasno, 2021), and these nutrients are essential factors for agricultural
59 sustainability (Wang et al., 2015; Salim and Raza, 2020). Therefore, maintaining or increasing
60 SOC content can enhance soil fertility and agricultural sustainability. However, this hypothesis
61 needs to be further checked across farming systems.

62 Soil C and nutrient (N, P, and K) contents are highly influenced by the choice of agricultural
63 systems. The implementation of poor farming practices such as deforestation, slash-and-burn,
64 shortening fallow periods, and conventional tillage has been reported to be detrimental to soil
65 quality (Gao et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2014; Kassa et al., 2017). It is unfortunate that knowing the
66 negative impacts of using these practices, some farmers still rely on them due to lack of resources.
67 This serious threat to agricultural sustainability should call the attention of policymakers,
68 scientists, and farmers. However, soil C and nutrient storage on agricultural land can be achieved
69 through agricultural systems such as agroforestry, fallow, mixed cropping, crop rotation,
70 conservation tillage, and cover cropping, crop residue incorporation (Yemefack, 2005; Zhang et
71 al., 2015). Unfortunately, there are limited studies on the ecological sustainability of these farming
72 systems.

73 Agroforestry is reported as an alternative to the problem of declining soil quality and a potential
74 strategy for climate change adaptation and mitigation (Kwesiga et al., 2003; Jose, 2009; Nair and
75 Nair, 2014). Likewise, crop rotation can lead to a yearly gain of about 67% SOC, 89% N, 150%
76 P, and 44% K (Alemayehu et al., 2020), while reduced tillage can lead to a gain of about 20%
77 SOC, 60% N, 09% P, and 17% K (Agbede, 2010; Yadav et al., 2019). Bravo-Garza and Bryan
78 (2005) reported a recovery of SOC and N by 34% and 62%, respectively, with 22 years of fallow,
79 while others observed improvements in as little as 7 years (Juo et al., 1995; Bowman et al., 1999).
80 Unfortunately, due to population increase that has led to land scarcity, fallow periods have
81 drastically dropped to about 5 years in rural areas and ≤ 4 years along major highways (Jalloh and
82 Njala, 2006; Kamara et al., 2016). Therefore, farming systems that adapt to the present conditions
83 should be enhanced through reliable studies.

84 The increasing demand for food caused by the increasing population exerts a lot of pressure on
85 natural resources. The world population is projected to reach 25 billion by the end of the 21st
86 century (Cleland, 2013) and more than 60% of Africa's population depends on soil resources
87 (Moyo, 2002). Thus, agriculture is growing to the detriment of the ecosystem (Yemefack et al.,
88 2006; Thornton et al., 2014), with drastic effects on soil fertility and crop yield (Albrecht and
89 Kandji, 2003; Dale and Polasky, 2007). About 70% of the population in Cameroon is employed in
90 the agricultural sector (Abia et al., 2016), and Cameroon which is part of SSA is endowed with
91 soils of high agronomic potential, but unfortunately, only 15.4% of these soils are exploited
92 (MINADER, 2012). Thus, the knowledge of soil resources and their agricultural potential is
93 required to promote sustainable and large-scale agricultural initiatives.

94 The forest-savanna-transition zone of Cameroon, characterized by different ecosystems (Onana,
95 2018), offers the possibility to cultivate perennial and annual crops. Perennial agriculture in the
96 area is mainly marked by cocoa agroforestry (Champaud, 1966) whereby cocoa is purposely
97 intercropped with several forests and highly valued tree species (Jagoret et al., 2009), while
98 subsistence agriculture in the area is characterized by the mixed cropping of groundnut (*Arachis*
99 *hypogea L.*), cassava (*Manihot esculenta Crantz*), corn (*Zea mays L.*), pumpkin (*Citrullus*
100 *colocynthis*), yam (*Dioscorea alata*), etc. (Kanmegne, 2004), managed under slash-and-burn,
101 conventional tillage, crop rotation, and fallow, etc. Here, farmers mainly rely on fallow for soil
102 nutrient recovery but unfortunately, fallow length is fast decreasing (≤ 5 years), with negative
103 consequences on yield (Kanmegne, 2004). However, more information is needed to prove the full
104 agronomic potential of the area to promote sustaining agricultural activities. Thus, this study aims
105 to characterize the agricultural systems present in the forest-savannah transition zone and assess
106 the variability and the relationship between soil SOC and nutrients (NPK).

107

108 2. Materials and Methods

109 2.1 Study area

110 The study area is located in the Mbam et Kim division in the central region of Cameroon, situated
111 about 100 km from Yaounde, the country's capital. The area lies between latitude 4°19' and 5°00'N
112 and longitude 11°30' and 11°50'E, covering a surface area of about 430 km². The prevailing
113 climate is the equatorial climate, and the area falls in the bimodal humid forest agroecological zone
114 of Cameroon characterized by two rainy seasons and two dry seasons. The major dry season goes
115 from mid-November to mid-March, while the minor dry season is from mid-June to mid-August.
116 The major rainy season goes from mid-August to mid-November and the minor rainy season is
117 from mid-March to mid-June. Total annual rainfall is estimated to be 1232 mm with temperatures
118 ranging between 23 °C and 28 °C (CLIMATE-DATA.org). Concerning the geomorphological
119 setting, the study area is in the Southern Cameroon Plateau, and it is characterized by an undulating
120 relief where planes, hills, and valleys alternate with an average altitude of 600 m. The vegetation
121 presents three distinct ecosystems namely: the semi-deciduous forest zone (FZ), the forest-
122 savannah transition zone (FSTZ), and the savannah zone (SZ), enabling the cultivation of perennial
123 and annual crops. The main group of in the study area is the Ferralsols (Onana, 2018). This soil is
124 shallow, more or less sandy, and characterized by a massive structure of very high porosity and
125 therefore need to be protected to limit the effects of erosion and leaching. Gleysols are also
126 observed at the bottom valleys. Fluvisols are observed along the borders of river Sanaga (Fig.1a).
127 Geologically, the area is located on para-metamorphic rocks characterized by several facies
128 namely: biotite embrechite, mica quartzite, two mica mica-schist, etc (Fig.1b).

129 (Insert Fig.1)

130 2.2 Survey

131 This study began with a door-to-door survey in the study area with the help of a well-structured
132 questionnaire. Both cocoa farmers and annual food crop farmers were interviewed about the
133 background and dynamics of the agricultural system in the area. About 13 villages were reached
134 during the survey (Nguila, Ossombe, Salakounou, Bivouna, Bilanga Kome, Bindalima I,
135 Bindalima II, Ntui center, Biastota, Ndjame, Nachtigal, Nguette, Kousse, Kele), and the number
136 of investigated farmers per village ranged between 15 and 25 based on the farmers' availability. A
137 total of 430 farmers were interviewed with 280 farmers on cocoa farming and 150 farmers on the
138 annual food crop farming. After each interview, the farmer's plot was visited for confirmation of
139 the information he/she provided which in most cases was true. The results of the survey helped in
140 the selection of the experimental plots for the study. The different farming systems were closely
141 monitored for two consecutive years (2021 and 2022) in the study area.

142 2.3 Selection of experimental plots

143 In cocoa agroforestry, three systems were defined in the study area based on ecosystem diversity
144 namely: the forest-based cocoa agroforestry (F_{cocoa}), savannah-based cocoa agroforestry (S_{cocoa}),
145 transition zone-based cocoa agroforestry (T_{cocoa}) (Fig. 2). In each ecosystem type, a transect was
146 defined comprising of three (03) experimental plots (03 replicates). The experiment plot size was
147 60×60 m, and the cocoa plots were old and aged between forty (40) and sixty (60) years.
148 Meanwhile, in the annual food crop system, four (04) mixed crop systems were defined based on
149 ecosystem diversity namely: the savannah mixed cropping of yam, pumpkin, and maize (S_{ypm}),
150 savannah mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava, and maize (S_{gcm}), transition zone mixed cropping
151 of yam, pumpkin, and maize (T_{ypm}), and the transition zone mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava,
152 and maize (T_{gcm}). The experimental plot size in the croplands was 20×20 m, and aged one year
153 from the start of the new farming cycle after the preceding fallow period but the lands have been
154 exploited for more than 20 years from the time the native vegetation was taken off. In the area, the
155 cropland is usually smaller in size (≤ 0.25 hectares) compared to the cocoa farms (1 to 30 hectares).

156 **(Insert Fig.2)**

157 2.4 Soil sampling

158 The soil samples were taken in April 2022. The soil was sampled at two depths namely 0 - 10 cm
159 (upper layer (UL)) and 10 - 30 cm (lower layer (LL)) using hand augers, and 2 kg of soil was
160 collected at each layer for laboratory analyses. The soil sampling methods in the agroforestry
161 system and cropping systems were different. In all the cocoa agroforestry systems, soil samples
162 were taken from 30 random sampling points in each experimental plot to form a composite sample
163 that was analyzed for physicochemical properties, and in total 18 composites (03 ecosystem types
164 \times 03 replicates \times 02 sampling depths) soil samples were taken. The annual crop fields both in the
165 transition and savannah zones are tilled to form mounds and ridges for crop production. The mixed
166 cropping system of yam-pumpkin-maize is grown on mounds while the mixed cropping system of
167 groundnut-cassava-maize is grown on ridges. Soil samples were taken from 20 sampling points at
168 the top of the mounds and ridges and in between (furrows) respectively to form a composite
169 sample, giving a total of 24 composite samples (02 ecosystem types \times 3 replicates \times 2 mixed
170 cropping systems \times 2 sampling depths). A total of 42 soil samples were collected for both the
171 agroforestry system and the annual cropping system. Bulk density was assessed using the core
172 method and one undisturbed soil sample was taken at each depth using core cylinders of 100 cm^3
173 . A total of 42 core samples were taken for bulk density measurements.

174 2.5 Soil analyses

175 Soil samples were air-dried at room temperature and passed through a 2 mm sieve. The chemical
176 analyses included soil organic carbon (OC), total nitrogen (TN), available phosphorus (P),
177 exchangeable potassium (K), pH, while the physical analyses included particle size distribution

178 and bulk density (Bd). For C and N analysis, soils were further ground to pass through a 0.5 mm
179 sieve. Organic C was determined by chromic acid digestion with heating and spectrophotometric
180 analysis (Heanes, 1984). Total N was determined from a wet acid digest (Buondonno et al., 1995)
181 and analyzed by colorimetric analysis (Anderson and Ingram, 1993), while K was extracted using
182 ammonium acetate at pH 7 and determined by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS).
183 For soil mineral N analysis, 5 – 10 g of fresh soil, depending on depth interval, was weighed into
184 a 50 ml extraction tube, and then 40 ml 1 M KCl was added inside. The soil was extracted end-
185 over-end for 30 min and then centrifuged at 302×g for 5 min. The supernatant was filtered through
186 a glass fiber filter (1.6 μm, VWR Europe). The concentrations of exchangeable NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻
187 were then measured colorimetrically by continuous flow analysis on an Autoanalyser III
188 (Bran+Luebbe, Germany) (Meng et al., 2022). Available P was extracted using the Bray-1
189 procedure and analyzed using the molybdate blue procedure described by Murphy and Riley
190 (1962). Soil pH in water was determined in a 1:5 (w/v) soil: water suspension. Particle size
191 distribution (sand, clay, and silt fractions) was determined by the hydrometer method (Day, 1965;
192 Boverwijk, 1967).

193 2.6 Calculation of bulk density (Bd), soil organic carbon stock (SOCS), and soil nitrogen stock
194 (SNS)

195 - *Bulk density*

196 Bulk density (g cm⁻³) was determined using the formula:

$$197 \quad Bd = \frac{DSW}{SV} \quad (1)$$

198 Where DSW is the dry soil weight; and SV is the soil volume.

199 - *Soil organic carbon stock (SOCS) and soil nitrogen stocks (SNS)*

200 SOCS (Mg ha⁻¹) and SNS (Mg ha⁻¹) were determined using the following equations (Chan, 2008):

$$201 \quad SOCS = SOC \times Bd \times SD \times 1000 \quad (2)$$

$$202 \quad SNS = TN \times Bd \times SD \times 1000 \quad (3)$$

203 Where SOC is the concentration of soil organic carbon (%), TN is the concentration of soil total
204 nitrogen (%), Bd is the bulk density (g cm⁻³); SD is the soil sampling depth (cm).

205 2.7 Statistical analyses

206 Data were tested for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk normality test and for equal variance using
207 Levene's test. Thereafter, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the effect
208 of the farming system on the measured soil variables (SOC, N, P, K, pH, Bd, SOCS, SNS, sand,

209 clay, and silt) followed by a post hoc test using “emmeans” (Lenth, 2022). The multiple
210 comparisons among the treatments were done using “multcomp” (Hothorn et al., 2008) and the p-
211 value was corrected for multiple comparisons with the “Sidak” adjustment. Linear regression
212 analysis was used to determine the relationship between SOC, N, and other soil parameters, and a
213 Student’s t-test was applied to assess the variation of the parameters with depth. Microsoft Excel
214 2016 and R Core Team (2023) were used to perform these analyses.

215 **3. Results**

216 3.1 Contrast between agricultural systems and management practices

217 3.1.1 *The cocoa agroforestry system*

218 Cocoa agroforestry was common in all three ecosystems (forest, savannah, and transition zone
219 ecosystems). Here, cocoa plants were purposely intercropped with high-valued tree species
220 including forest trees (woody and medicinal trees) that were left on the land during the preparation
221 phase and planted fruit trees. The main difference between the different cocoa agroforestry systems
222 lies in the density and diversity of the intercropped trees. Thus, the forest-based cocoa agroforestry
223 (F_{cocoa}) is characterized by a relatively higher density and more diversified species of intercropped
224 forest and fruit trees, while the transition zone-based cocoa agroforestry (T_{cocoa}) is characterized
225 by a lesser density and species of forest and fruit trees, and the savannah-based cocoa (S_{cocoa}) is
226 mainly intercropped with fruit trees. The table below summarizes the information on the species
227 of intercropped trees recorded in the experimental plots.

228 **(Insert Table.1)**

229 3.1.2 *The annual food crop system*

230 Annual food crop cultivation is mainly practiced in the savannah and transition zones. Annual
231 cropping in both areas is characterized by two rotational mixed cropping systems namely the
232 mixed cropping of groundnut (*Arachis hypogea L.*), cassava (*Manihot esculenta Crantz*), and
233 maize (*Zea mays L.*) in the savannah (S_{gcm}), and transition zone (T_{gcm}), and the mixed cropping
234 system of yam (*Dioscorea alata*), pumpkin (*Citrullus colocynthis*), and maize (*Zea mays L.*) still
235 in the savannah (S_{ypm}) and the transition zone (T_{ypm}). The main differences between the annual
236 crop systems of the savannah and the transition zone lie in the fallow length, the intensity of tillage,
237 and the frequency of the mixed crop rotation. Thus, contrarily to the savannah zone, the fallow
238 length is relatively shorter in the transition zone, with frequent tillage and a higher frequency of
239 mixed crop rotation.

240 3.2 Variability of agricultural management practices

241 *3.2.1 Cocoa agroforestry systems*

242 The main agricultural practices noted in this sector included slash-and-burn, felling down of trees,
243 clearing, pruning or health harvesting, maintenance using the anti-capsid treatment and brown rot
244 treatment, and harvesting. Thus, activities usually start with the felling down of trees, followed by
245 slash-and-burn and clearing which takes place in January, February, June, July, November, and
246 December, while planting takes place between late February - early June, and late July - early
247 November. For the existing plantations, pruning or health harvesting, anti-capsid treatment, and
248 brown rot treatment take place between January and February, and harvest usually starts from late
249 October to late December. Cocoa plantations are composed of local and improved cocoa varieties
250 and farmers get their seed from either supporting organizations or previous harvests which they
251 use to build up their nurseries. Farmers apply the same management techniques with slight
252 differences at the level of the frequencies conditioned by ecological factors and the financial
253 abilities of the farmers. Farmers do not use granular fertilizer due to financial constraints but a few
254 farmers said they do not need it because of the negative impacts it may cause to the soil quality in
255 the long term.

256 *3.2.2 Annual food crop systems*

257 Added to the results of the survey, activities were also closely monitored in the annual crop fields.
258 Thus, the annual cropping system in the study area is characterized by rotational mixed cropping
259 depending on natural soil fertility recovery from fallow with no use of pesticides. Farms are
260 managed in poverty through the practice of slash-and-burn, associated with conventional tillage,
261 crop residue incorporation, crop rotation, and fallow. Here, farming generally begins with the
262 conversion of native lands or fallow fields through slash-and-burn and clearing. After clearing, the
263 soil is tilled to produce mounds for the first group of crops generally composed of yam, pumpkin,
264 and maize (T_{ypm} and S_{ypm}). Thus, soil preparation takes place between late January to early March,
265 with sowing from late March to early April, weeding from late April to June, and harvesting in
266 early July. After harvesting this first group of crops, the farmers get rid of the crop residues, and
267 the soil is tilled once more to form ridges that will receive the next set of crops generally composed
268 of groundnut, cassava, and maize. Groundnut and maize are the first to be harvested and the
269 residues are kept at the feet of the growing cassava plants to control evapotranspiration and to
270 improve soil nutrient content after decomposition. This second group of crops can be repeatedly
271 planted 2 to 3 times on the same plot, after which the plot is left on fallow for about two to five
272 years. The bimodal rainfall regime in the area gives the possibility for farmers to carry out two
273 farming cycles annually for corn and groundnut.

274 3.3 Soil physical and chemical properties

275 3.3.1 Soil chemical properties

276 3.1.1.1 Soil organic carbon (SOC), total nitrogen (N), Nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+)

277 The difference in the concentration of SOC was significant ($p < 0.02$) across the agricultural
278 systems in the upper layer (UL), and it was higher in the agroforestry system than the croplands
279 with the highest concentration in F_{cocoa} (25.1 g kg^{-1}), followed by S_{cocoa} (22.5 g kg^{-1}) and then T_{cocoa}
280 (19.2 g kg^{-1}). Meanwhile, in the croplands, SOC was relatively higher in the transition zone with
281 15.4 g kg^{-1} for T_{ypm} and 13.03 g kg^{-1} for T_{gcm} (Fig. 3a).

282 As indicated in Fig. 3b, the test for N also showed a significant difference across the farming
283 systems both in UL ($p < 0.001$) and LL ($p < 0.02$), with a greater magnitude in the UL. Thus,
284 unlike SOC, the concentration of N was higher in agroforestry both in UL and LL with the highest
285 concentration in UL recorded in F_{cocoa} (2.3 g kg^{-1}), followed by S_{cocoa} (1.8 g kg^{-1}), and then the
286 T_{cocoa} (1.6 g kg^{-1}), and the same order applies for LL with 1.5 g kg^{-1} , 1.3 g kg^{-1} , 1.1 g kg^{-1}
287 respectively. In the croplands, the highest concentrations of N were also recorded in the transition
288 zone with 0.9 g kg^{-1} and 0.6 g kg^{-1} for T_{ypm} , and 0.9 g kg^{-1} and 0.7 g kg^{-1} for T_{gcm} in UL and LL
289 respectively (Fig. 3b). From the above results SOC and N present similar trends across the different
290 agricultural systems and both in the UL and LL indicating a strong positive correlation between
291 the two parameters (Fig. 4 a and b).

292 **(Insert Fig.3 and Fig.4)**

293 The respective soil tests showed no significant differences in Soil NO_3^- and NH_4^+ across the
294 farming systems but in both cases, a greater magnitude was noted in UL. Soil NO_3^- showed a
295 similar trend as N and OC in both UL and LL where the highest concentrations were noted in
296 agroforestry with 4.60 mg kg^{-1} and 4.52 mg kg^{-1} in F_{cocoa} and T_{cocoa} respectively. Higher
297 concentrations of NH_4^+ were also noted in agroforestry but with the highest rather in T_{cocoa} (3.63
298 mg kg^{-1}) followed by F_{cocoa} (3.21 mg kg^{-1}). In the croplands, the highest concentration of NO_3^-
299 (2.58 mg kg^{-1}) and NH_4^+ (2.57 mg kg^{-1}) were noted in the transition zone (Table 2). Thus, positive
300 correlations were also observed between OC and N and ammonium (NH_4^+) (Fig. 4 c and e) and
301 nitrate (NO_3^-) (Fig. 4 d and f) in the upper soil layers and NO_3^- and N (Fig. 5 a), and SOC (Fig. 5
302 b), and available phosphorus (P) (c), in the lower soil layers across agricultural systems in the
303 study area.

304 **(Insert Table. 2)**

305 3.3.1.2 Soil organic carbon stocks (SOCS) and soil nitrogen stock (SNS)

306 Like in the case of SOC, the difference in SOCS in the UL was significant ($p < 0.01$) across the
307 different farming systems. Thus, in the UL, SOCS was higher in the agroforestry system than the
308 croplands, with the highest concentration in F_{cocoa} (32.1 Mg ha^{-1}), followed by S_{cocoa} (30.0 Mg ha^{-1})

309 ¹) and lastly T_{cocoa} (25.6 Mg ha^{-1}). Meanwhile, in the cropland, SOCS was higher in the transition
310 zone with 19.7 Mg ha^{-1} for T_{ypm} , and 17.5 Mg ha^{-1} for T_{gcm} (Fig. 6).

311 **(Insert Fig. 6)**

312 In the same way, SNS showed a significant difference across the farming systems and management
313 practices both in the UL ($p \leq 0.001$) and the LL ($p \leq 0.01$), but with a higher magnitude in the UL.
314 Thus, SNS was higher in cocoa agroforestry over the croplands in both UL and LL with the highest
315 concentration in F_{cocoa} , followed by S_{cocoa} , and then the T_{cocoa} showing 2.9 Mg ha^{-1} , 2.4 Mg ha^{-1} ,
316 and 2.1 Mg ha^{-1} in the UL and 4.9 Mg ha^{-1} , 3.6 Mg ha^{-1} , and 3.0 Mg ha^{-1} in the LL respectively. In
317 the croplands, the highest concentrations were recorded in the transition zone (T_{ypm} and T_{gcm}), with
318 1.4 Mg ha^{-1} and 1.2 Mg ha^{-1} in the UL, and 2.5 Mg ha^{-1} and 2.0 Mg ha^{-1} in the LL respectively
319 (Fig. 7).

320 **(Insert Fig. 7)**

321 The test on the variability of soil parameters with soil depth showed significant differences ($p <$
322 0.04) in SOCS and SNS only in the annual cropping systems, with a greater magnitude in S_{gcm} for
323 SOCS ($p < 0.01$).

324 *3.3.1.3 Available phosphorus (P), exchangeable potassium (K), C:N ratio, bulk density (Bd),*
325 *and pHwater*

326 **(Insert Table. 2)**

327 The soil P and K showed no significant differences across the farming systems both in the UL and
328 the LL. However, the trend of K in both UL and LL is similar to that of SOC and N thereby
329 indicating a positive correlation as indicated by the linear regression model below (Fig. 8 a, b, c
330 and d). A positive correlation was also observed between P and NO_3^- (see Fig. 5 c).

331 **(Insert Fig.8)**

332 Soil pH also showed a significant difference ($p < 0.01$) across the farming systems in UL, with the
333 highest value in the F_{cocoa} , followed by the S_{cocoa} and then the T_{cocoa} . Meanwhile, in the croplands,
334 the highest pH values for both UL and LL were recorded in the savannah with a significant
335 difference in depth ($p\text{-value} < 0.01$) in S_{gcm} (Table 3). Thus, pH follows the same trend as SOC
336 and N in the agroforestry system (Fig. 8 e and f)

337 The C:N ratio showed a significant difference ($p < 0.002$) across the farming systems and was
338 higher in the annual croplands (Table 3).

339 **(Insert Table. 3)**

340 3.3.2 Soil physical properties (soil texture and bulk density)

341 The soils of the different farming systems show almost similar texture classes in both UL and LL.
342 All the cocoa agroforestry soils have a sandy-loam texture except for the subsoil of S_{cocoa} which
343 showed a sandy-clay texture. In the croplands, the transition zone shows a sandy-clay_loam texture
344 in both UL and LL, while the savannah shows a sandy-loam texture.

345 (see Fig.S1 of supplementary material)

346 The Bd showed a significant difference across the different farming systems in the UL ($p < 0.01$)
347 and LL ($p < 0.03$). Thus, the highest Bd for the UL was noted in the savannah cropland (S_{ypm}) with
348 1.41 g cm^{-3} , while the highest value for Bd for the LL was noted in agroforestry (F_{cocoa}) (see Table
349 3).

350 3.4 Variation of soil properties with depth

351 The variation of soil parameters with depth across the farming systems and ecosystems was mainly
352 significant in the croplands for pH, SOCS, and SNS ($p < 0.05$), with a higher magnitude ($p < 0.01$)
353 in S_{gcm} . thus, the concentration of these parameters decreased from UL to LL. However, a
354 significant difference was noted from UL to LL in F_{cocoa} for Bd ($p < 0.04$).

355 4. Discussion

356 4.1 Variability of soil physicochemical properties across farming systems

357 4.1.1 Soil organic carbon (SOC)

358 The relatively higher concentration of OC in cocoa agroforestry over croplands is probably the
359 result of the decomposition of litter from the cocoa plants, the intercropped forest trees, and shrubs,
360 (Keesstra et al., 2018; Kassa et al., 2017; Yimer et al., 2007; Worku et al., 2014). It may also result
361 from the dead fine tree, shrub roots, and the mycorrhizal fungi contribution of SOM confirming
362 the studies of Lemma et al. (2006), and Yimer et al. (2007). The highest concentration of SOC was
363 noted in the forest cocoa agroforestry system (F_{cocoa}) which may be due to the relatively higher
364 density of intercropped forest and fruit trees of different species, compared to the cocoa
365 agroforestry plantations of the savannah and the transition zones showing similar results with those
366 of the study of Cerda et al. (2014). Thus, litter is subjected to microbial processes and
367 decomposition which release soil C and nutrients from organic matter and soil minerals as reported
368 by Rao et al. (1997) and Bayala and Prieto (2020). Meanwhile, the relatively low concentration of
369 SOC in the croplands may result from the slash-and-burn practice, which is accompanied by short
370 fallow periods (≤ 5 years). Here, farmers rely on slash-and-burn for clearing due to poverty. Thus,
371 they are obliged to survive under conditions of inadequate resources. Slash-and-burn can cause
372 loss of biodiversity, decrease in SOM content, aggregate stability, soil nutrient depletion, increase
373 in surface runoff, soil erosion, and leaching reflecting the studies of Cox et al. (2000) and

374 Yemefack et al. (2006). Slash and burn also cause high release of CO₂ gas into the atmosphere
375 thereby contributing to climate change as reported by Palm et al. (2004).

376 On the other hand, the relatively higher concentrations of OC in the transition zone over the
377 savannah ecosystem (Figure 3a) can be explained by the difference in fallow length, the intensity
378 of tillage, and the duration of the crop rotational system. Fallow length is relatively shorter (1 - 3
379 years) in the transition zone with more frequent tillage and crop rotation phases. Thus, enough
380 crop residues are generated from the frequent crop rotation, and tillage facilitates crop residue
381 incorporation into the soil which undergoes decomposition under the action of micro-organisms
382 to release OC from the SOM into the soil (Jarecki and Lal, 2003; Blanco-Canqui and Wortmann,
383 2017). Crop residues are generally composed of stalks, stubble, leaves, roots, and seed pods, which
384 determine the SOM content and the availability of nutrients when they undergo decomposition
385 under favorable conditions as enunciated by Samake et al. (2005), Nicholson et al. (2014), Khan
386 et al. (2021). Thus, the transition zone is situated along the highway and therefore the relatively
387 shorter fallow length is probably due to the higher population density and high demand for food
388 leading to land scarcity and tenure confirming the studies of Jalloh and Njala (2006). These authors
389 reported that fallow length has dropped to about 5 years in rural areas and 3 - 4 years along major
390 highways. On the other hand, the lower concentration of OC in the savannah croplands with longer
391 fallow periods (5 years) may also be due to the high bulk density (Table 3). The human actions
392 and livestock grazing during the fallow period contribute to limiting the SOM input into the soil,
393 causing soil compaction with a negative impact on the soil bulk density as enunciated in the
394 findings of Hamza and Anderson (2005) and Don et al. (2011).

395 *4.1.2 Total nitrogen (N), total nitrogen (N), Nitrate (NO₃⁻), ammonium (NH₄⁺), available* 396 *phosphorus (P)*

397 The relatively high concentrations of N, NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, and P in agroforestry and more precisely in
398 F_{cocoa} are probably due to the high litter fall from the denser intercropped leguminous and non-
399 leguminous trees, shrubs, and herbs, following the findings of Yimer et al. (2007) and Worku et
400 al. (2014). The leguminous tree species play a significant role in supplying SOM, N, and P to the
401 soil as reported by Nsabimana et al. (2008) and Worku et al. (2014). This also explains the positive
402 correlation between N and OC (Figure 4). The decreasing concentrations of N and P from F_{cocoa} to
403 T_{cocoa} and then S_{cocoa} are certainly due to the decreasing density and species of the intercropped
404 leguminous trees. Also, the relatively higher concentration of N and P in agroforestry may be
405 related to the use of foliar fertilizers by a few cocoa farmers, although randomly applied in most
406 cases due to financial constraints. The C:N ratio is relatively lower in agroforestry (Table 3) which
407 may also favor SOM decomposition confirming the hypothesis of Cai et al. (2022) stating that the
408 higher the C:N ratio, the longer the time needed for material decomposition.

409 Meanwhile, the relatively lower concentrations of N and P in the croplands might be the result of
410 leaching and surface erosion reflecting the findings of Nsabimana et al. (2008) and Abegaz and
411 Adugna (2015). In both the savannah and transition zones, the mixed cropping systems of yam,

412 pumpkin, and maize (T_{ypm} and S_{ypm}) show higher concentrations of N over the mixed cropping
413 system of T_{gcm} and S_{gcm} . The best explanation for this can be the fact that T_{ypm} and S_{ypm} are the
414 first cropping systems usually put in place after the period of fallow which is usually terminated
415 by slash-and-burn. The ash from the slash-and-burn practice acts as lime fertilizer at the beginning
416 of the cropping period which can help in ameliorating soil nutrient contents and acidity correction
417 based on the reports of Juo and Manu (1996) and Yemefack et al. (2002), though these nutrients
418 are usually temporally available for plant uptake. Besides, fallow can lead to an increase in soil N
419 due to the decomposition of the fallow vegetation (above-ground and root biomass) including
420 leguminous plant species as reported by Samake et al. (2005). Meanwhile, the concentration of
421 available P was relatively higher in the mixed cropping system of groundnut, cassava, and maize
422 (S_{gcm}). This may be due to the presence of groundnut which is a leguminous cover crop. Cover
423 crops are good at protecting the soil from erosion and soil nutrient loss through leaching and run-
424 off as mentioned in the findings of Kuo and Sainju (1998) and Khan et al. (2021). Cover crops
425 also ameliorated soil structure increasing SOM content, thereby enhancing soil nutrient availability
426 and this matches the findings of Hubbard et al. (2013), and Khan et al. (2021).

427 *4.1.3 Exchangeable potassium (K)*

428 The high concentration of K in agroforestry more precisely in S_{cocoa} may be due to the presence of
429 high organic matter and clay contents showing the sandy clay texture in the UL (Table 2), from
430 which the organic matter formed by trees and shrubs litter underwent a complete microbial
431 breakdown and decomposition, releasing humic substances and exchangeable bases reflecting the
432 studies of Saikh et al. (1998) and Nsabimana et al. (2008). Thus, there exists a strong correlation
433 between K with SOC and N (Fig.7 and Fig. 8). These authors also stated that the high concentration
434 of K may result from the type of parent material. Thus, parent material with a relatively high
435 content of mica will release potassium in an available form at a more rapid rate than parent
436 materials relatively high in feldspar.

437 Unlike SOC and N, K was generally higher in the transition zone (T_{ypm} and T_{gcm}) than in the
438 savannah zone (S_{ypm} and S_{gcm}). Meanwhile, the transition zone is characterized by relatively
439 shorter fallow periods of 1 to 3 years compared to the savannah (5 years). Therefore, the relatively
440 higher concentration of K may be the result of the decomposition and retention of crop residue
441 input from frequent cultivation and the relatively shorter fallow length.

442 *4.1.4 Soil organic carbon stock (SOCS) and soil nitrogen stock (SNS)*

443 The higher SOCS and SNS in the F_{cocoa} might also be a result of the continuous leaf defoliation
444 from trees and shrubs. Thus, a good number of leguminous tree species could lead to the
445 accumulation of high SOCS and SNS in the agroforestry systems. Findings have revealed that the
446 carbon fixed in the tissue of leguminous trees contributes a lot to surface and subsurface soil in the
447 form of detritus upon seasonal defoliation and senescence (Mohammed and Bekele, 2014; Lal,
448 2001. Binkley and Giardina (1998) further highlighted that this is a common phenomenon in the

449 tropical area that holds leguminous trees. Meanwhile, the existence of low SOCS and SNS in the
450 cropland may be due to nutrient uptake by plants, leaching, and surface erosion losses. It might
451 also be due to agricultural management practices such as conventional tillage and grazing after
452 harvest as stated by Lemenih (2004) and Don et al. (2011).

453 On the other hand, a significant difference was noted in the variation of SOCS in the croplands
454 with a greater magnitude in S_{gcm} which is the second set of crops put in place in the cropping cycle.
455 This may be the result of slash-and-burn and tillage practices which cause the disintegration of soil
456 aggregates thereby enhancing the leaching of nutrients and the emission of CO_2 leading to soil C
457 losses, especially in the upper soil layer of soil as reported by Du Preez et al. (2001), Roldán et al.
458 (2003), and D'Haene et al. (2008).

459 4.2 Variation of soil parameters with soil depth across the farming systems

460 The significant difference in soil pH, SOCS, and SNS content in the croplands may be the result
461 of the agricultural management practices. Thus, croplands are managed under slash-and-burn,
462 conventional tillage, and shortened fallow lengths of ≤ 5 years (Kanmegne, 2004). Slash-and-burn
463 may cause damage to the upper soil layer because fire hinders soil C storage, carbon allocation
464 patterns, and plant tissue chemistry, and decreases the rate of SOM decomposition (Reich et al.,
465 2001).

466 4.3 Dynamics of agricultural systems and management practices

467 4.3.1 Cocoa agroforestry

468 The diversity in the cocoa agroforestry systems in the study area is conditioned by the existing
469 ecological factors and the desire for the farmers to improve the sustainability of their livelihood.
470 Thus, the vegetation presents three distinct ecosystems that determine diversity in the cocoa
471 agroforestry systems namely the semi-deciduous forest, the forest-savannah transition zone, and
472 the savannah (Onana, 2018). The forest ecosystem was composed of denser and more diversified
473 forest tree species that are gradually being replaced by cocoa plantations. This explains why the
474 forest-based agroforestry systems (F_{cocoa}) were composed of complex associations of multi-
475 functional and uneven-aged trees left after land preparation and planted fruit trees with a few large
476 trees as reported by Jagoret et al. (2012). The forest-based cocoa agroforestry also showed a
477 complex spatial and temporal structure which can be seen as a sustainable alternative to intensive
478 agricultural systems (Tscharntke et al., 2012; Bieng et al., 2013). The density and diversity of
479 intercropped trees decreased when moving to the cocoa agroforestry (T_{cocoa}) of the transition zone.
480 The savannah ecosystem was composed of scattered shrubs of about 2m of height which are
481 eliminated to set up the savannah-based cocoa agroforestry (S_{cocoa}) which is composed mainly of
482 cocoa plants and planted fruit trees (Letouzey, 1968; Jagoret et al., 2012). Farmers in the area
483 depend on agroforestry for subsistence, economic income, and other services from the sales of
484 agroforestry products (timber, firewood, and fruits) matching the findings of Cerda et al. (2014)

485 and Paul et al. (2017). However, the economic productivity and profitability of cocoa agroforestry
486 farms are not fully assessed (Lamanda et al., 2012; Cerda et al., 2014).

487 *4.3.2 Annual croplands*

488 Annual food crop cultivation, practised in the savannah and transition zone, is managed under a
489 mixed crop rotational system involving slash and burn, tillage, crop residue retention, and fallow.
490 Thus, the choice of agricultural systems and management practices was conditioned by population
491 pressure, agricultural land shortage and land tenure, and poverty, while the choice of the type of
492 crop to grow was mainly determined by income, the availability of the market, family sustenance.
493 Land shortage and land tenure lead to shortening fallow periods which reduces the regrowth and
494 amount of vegetation, thereby decreasing the amount of C and nutrient (NPK) inputs for fertility
495 restoration reflecting the studies of Aguilera et al. (2013). Poverty pushes farmers to rely on slash-
496 and-burn for clearing large surfaces at low cost which may result in loss of biodiversity, decrease
497 in SOM, soil nutrient depletion, and surface runoff, reflecting the works of Cox et al. (2000),
498 Yemefcak et al. (2006). Farmers practice crop rotation involving legumes (groundnut) mainly to
499 ensure crop variability and a balanced diet but studies have reported that it also helps to improve
500 soil structure (Raimbault and Vyn, 1991), soil C, and nutrient storage (Campbell and Zentner,
501 2019), minimizing the use of fertilizers (Riedell et al., 2009), and conventional tillage which can
502 cause modification of soil structure, floral and faunal communities (Plante and McGill, 2002), and
503 high losses of soil C and nutrients (N, P, and K), thereby contributing to climate change (Roldán
504 et al., 2003). Farmers reported that crop residue retention controls evapotranspiration and promote
505 SOM content, availability of nutrients, and soil aggregate stability in line with the findings of
506 Villamil et al. (2015).

507

508 **5. Conclusion**

509 Cocoa agroforestry has a higher potential for SOC, N, and P storage than croplands with a higher
510 magnitude in the forest-based cocoa agroforestry marked by higher density and species of
511 intercropped forest and fruit trees. Meanwhile, croplands have low nutrient content which is
512 probably caused by slash-and-burn, tillage, and shortening fallow. In the croplands, SOC, N, and
513 K were relatively higher in the transition zone than in the savannah, which may result from the
514 frequent decomposition of crop residues. On the other hand, the savannah croplands with longer
515 fallow lengths showed high soil bulk density which is probably the result of soil compaction caused
516 by livestock grazing. Furthermore, in both the savannah and transition zone, the mixed crop system
517 of yam, pumpkin, and maize (T_{ypm} and S_{ypm}) indicated a higher concentration of K in the soils.
518 This is the first set of crops that is planted after the fallow phase and is usually ended with slash-
519 and-burn. Therefore, the higher concentration of K may result from fallow and slash-and-burn.
520 Meanwhile, the mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava, and maize (T_{gcm} and S_{gcm}) showed a higher
521 concentration of P which may be due to the presence of groundnut (cover crop) which limits the
522 threat of leaching on P and the decomposition of the litter of the previous crops (T_{ypm} and S_{ypm}).
523 Therefore, nutrient content in croplands may be improved under mixed cropping involving cover
524 crops and leguminous crop species, crop rotation, reduced tillage, crop residue incorporation,
525 fallow, and slash-and-burn. Nevertheless, prolonged periods of experimentation with more
526 replicates and sampling depths are required to show quantitative evidence of the long-term effects
527 of these agricultural practices, and the overall benefits of intercropped trees on soil quality and
528 ecosystem functioning in agroforestry for more reliability in the results. Future studies should also
529 consider mapping out the areas of the different ecosystems for a better appreciation of the
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537 **Data availability**

538 Data will be made available on request.

539 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

540 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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Table 1

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List of intercropped trees in the cocoa agroforestry systems

Agroforestry system	Experimental plots	Tree specie	Local names	Scientific names	Number		
F _{cocoa}	Plot one	Forest	Dabema	<i>Piptadeniastrum africanum</i>	2		
			Efok	<i>Cola millenii</i>	1		
			Gangsang	<i>Ricinodendron heudelottii</i>	2		
			Frake	<i>Terminalia superba</i>	2		
			Shinglewood	<i>Terminalia superba</i>	1		
			African coralwood	<i>Pterocarpus soyauxii</i>	3		
		Fruit	Banana tree	<i>Musa spp</i>	3		
			Palm tree	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	3		
			Plum tree	<i>Dacryodes edulis</i>	1		
			Lime tree	<i>Citrus limon</i>	2		
			Plot two	Forest	African corkwood tree	<i>Musanga cecropioides</i>	2
					Monkey cola	<i>Milicia excelsa</i>	3
					African coralwood	<i>Pterocarpus soyauxii</i>	3
				Fruit	Cheese maker	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	1
	Banana tree	<i>Musa spp</i>			1		
	Pear tree	<i>Persea americana</i>			4		
	Plot three	Forest	African corkwood tree	<i>Musanga cecropioides</i>	1		
			Frake	<i>Terminalia superba</i>	1		
			Fruit	Golden apple	<i>Spondias cytharea</i>	3	
		Pear tree		<i>Persea americana</i>	2		
Banana tree		<i>Musa spp</i>		3			
Orange tree		<i>Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck</i>	3				
T _{cocoa}	Plot one	Forest	African whitewood	<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i>	2		
			Iroko	<i>Milicia excelsa</i>	1		
		Fruit	Monkey cola	<i>Cola millenii</i>	2		
			Banana tree	<i>Musa spp</i>	2		
	Plot two	Forest	Teque	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	2		
			Iroko	<i>Milicia excelsa</i>	1		

		Fruit	Plum tree	<i>Dacryodes edulis</i>	2
			Banana tree	<i>Musa spp</i>	2
	Plot three	Forest	Blush macaranga	<i>Macaranga barteri Mull</i>	1
		Fruit	Bitter cola	<i>Garcinia afzelii kola</i>	2
			Pear tree	<i>Persea americana</i>	2
			Mango tree	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	3
S _{cocoa}	Plot one	Fruit	Orange tree	<i>Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck</i>	2
			Banana tree	<i>Musa spp</i>	2
	Plot two	Fruit	Palm tree	<i>Palmier à huile</i>	2
			Banana tree	<i>Musa spp</i>	3
	Plot three	Fruit	Palm tree	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	2
			Banana tree	<i>Musa spp</i>	3
			Plum tree	<i>Dacryodes edulis</i>	1

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Table 2

Soil nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+) available phosphorus (P), and exchangeable potassium (K) across different agricultural systems.

Soil layers/A. S	NO_3^- (mg kg ⁻¹)		NH_4^+ (mg kg ⁻¹)		P (mg kg ⁻¹)		K (mg kg ⁻¹)	
	UL	LL	UL	LL	UL	LL	UL	LL
F _{cocoa}	4.60 ± 0.85	2.20 ± 1.10	3.21 ± 0.11	2.87 ± 0.28	5.11 ± 2.34	3.31 ± 1.55	117.8 ± 35.5	88.0 ± 28.3
T _{cocoa}	4.52 ± 1.73	1.81 ± 0.80	3.63 ± 0.59	2.70 ± 0.59	1.98 ± 0.16	1.37 ± 0.21	103.5 ± 17.5	65.4 ± 10.1
S _{cocoa}	2.03 ± 0.69	0.59 ± 0.03	2.99 ± 0.40	2.69 ± 0.20	0.90 ± 0.09	0.62 ± 0.06	129.9 ± 61.8	129.3 ± 61.8
T _{ypm}	2.58 ± 0.39	1.76 ± 0.24	2.57 ± 0.45	2.82 ± 0.51	2.20 ± 0.56	1.63 ± 0.41	176.9 ± 90.7	125.1 ± 44.1
T _{gcm}	1.79 ± 0.21	1.00 ± 0.12	2.29 ± 0.30	2.59 ± 0.06	1.90 ± 0.19	1.40 ± 0.08	76.9 ± 16.0	69.1 ± 13.6
S _{ypm}	1.39 ± 0.42	0.52 ± 0.29	2.17 ± 0.35	3.06 ± 0.44	2.66 ± 0.48	1.82 ± 0.08	61.3 ± 23.7	49.5 ± 19.2
S _{gcm}	1.68 ± 0.12	1.29 ± 0.04	2.09 ± 0.16	2.41 ± 0.13	3.27 ± 0.68	2.69 ± 0.41	56.0 ± 16.0	50.8 ± 18.5

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UL = upper soil layer, LL = lower soil layer, A.S = agricultural systems, P = available phosphorus, K = exchangeable potassium, NO_3^- = Nitrate, NH_4^+ = Ammonium, and the mean values with the same letter within the same layer are not significantly different from each other.

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Table 3
Soil C:N ratio, bulk density (Bd), and pH

Soil layers/A.S	C:N		Bd (g cm ⁻³)		pH	
	UL	LL	UL	LL	UL	LL
F _{cocoa}	10.8 ± 0.47c	11.1 ± 0.39c	1.30 ± 0.04a	1.60 ± 0.06a	7.35 ± 0.14a	6.99 ± 0.06a
T _{cocoa}	11.9 ± 0.83bc	12.3 ± 1.38bc	1.34 ± 0.10a	1.37 ± 0.11a	5.72 ± 0.38b	5.42 ± 0.21b
S _{cocoa}	12.3 ± 0.75abc	12.3 ± 0.20ab	1.35 ± 0.07a	1.33 ± 0.04a	6.13 ± 0.35b	5.86 ± 0.15b
T _{ypm}	13.1 ± 0.25abc	14.4 ± 0.59bc	1.30 ± 0.10a	1.34 ± 0.07a	5.40 ± 0.13ab	5.20 ± 0.08b
T _{gem}	14.3 ± 0.32abc	15.1 ± 0.27abc	1.33 ± 0.12a	1.31 ± 0.04a	5.33 ± 0.14b	5.26 ± 0.25b
S _{ypm}	16.4 ± 0.68a	16.9 ± 0.54a	1.41 ± 0.09a	1.54 ± 0.02a	5.97 ± 0.22b	5.55 ± 0.13b
S _{gem}	15.5 ± 1.66 ab	16.7 ± 1.09a	1.25 ± 0.09a	1.38 ± 0.04a	6.08 ± 0.05b	5.67 ± 0.04b

860 UL = upper soil layer, LL = lower soil layer, A.S = agricultural systems, C:N = the ratio of carbon on nitrogen, Bd = bulk density, Mean
861 values with the same letter within the same layer are not significantly different from each other
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 865 **Fig. 1.** Location map (a) and geologic map (b) of the study area extracted from the geologic map of Cameroon (Gauss projection
 866 International meridian to 1/200.000 of S.G.A.E.F-Cameroon, 1949).

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Fig. 2. Landsat image of the study area (2022) showing the distribution of the ecosystems and farming systems

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 872 **Fig. 3.** Variation of (a) soil organic carbon (SOC) and (b) total nitrogen (N) across different
 873 agricultural systems in the study area F_{cocoa} = forest-based cocoa agroforestry, S_{cocoa} = savannah-
 874 based cocoa agroforestry, T_{cocoa} = transition zone-based cocoa agroforestry, S_{ypm} = savannah mixed
 875 cropping of yam, pumpkin, and maize, S_{gcm} = savannah mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava,
 876 and maize, transition zone mixed T_{ypm} = cropping of yam, pumpkin, and maize, T_{gcm} = transition
 877 zone mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava, and maize, Differently lettered means indicate
 878 significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the agricultural systems for a given soil layer

879
 880 **Fig. 4.** Simple linear regression showing positive correlations ($p < 0.005$) between total nitrogen
 881 (N) (a and b), ammonium (NH_4^+) (c and e), Nitrate (NO_3^-) (d and f), and soil organic carbon (SOC)
 882 in the upper and lower soil layers across agricultural systems in the study area.

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 884 **Fig. 5.** Simple linear regression showing positive correlations ($p < 0.005$) between nitrate (NO_3^-)
 885 and total nitrogen (N) (a), soil organic carbon (SOC) (b), and available phosphorus (P) (c), in the
 886 lower soil layers across agricultural systems in the study area.
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 890 **Fig. 6.** Variation of soil organic carbon stock (SOCS) across farming systems
 891 F_{cocoa} = forest-based cocoa agroforestry, S_{cocoa} = savannah-based cocoa agroforestry, T_{cocoa} =
 892 transition zone-based cocoa agroforestry, S_{ypm} = savannah mixed cropping of yam, pumpkin, and
 893 maize, S_{gcm} = savannah mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava, and maize, transition zone mixed
 894 T_{ypm} = cropping of yam, pumpkin, and maize, T_{gcm} = transition zone mixed cropping of groundnut,
 895 cassava, and maize, Differently lettered means indicate significant differences (p < 0.05) between
 896 the agricultural systems for a given soil layer
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 899 **Fig. 7.** Variation of soil nitrogen stock (SNS) across different agricultural systems
 900 F_{cocoa} = forest-based cocoa agroforestry, S_{cocoa} = savannah-based cocoa agroforestry, T_{cocoa} =
 901 transition zone-based cocoa agroforestry, S_{ypm} = savannah mixed cropping of yam, pumpkin, and
 902 maize, S_{gcm} = savannah mixed cropping of groundnut, cassava, and maize, transition zone mixed
 903 T_{ypm} = cropping of yam, pumpkin, and maize, T_{gcm} = transition zone mixed cropping of groundnut,
 904 cassava, and maize, Differently lettered means indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between
 905 the agricultural systems for a given soil layer
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 908 **Fig. 8.** Simple linear regression showing positive correlations ($p < 0.005$) between exchangeable
 909 potassium (K) and soil organic carbon (SOC) (a and b) and total nitrogen (N) (c and d), and
 910 between pH and SOC (e), and total nitrogen (N) (f) in the upper and lower soil layers across
 911 agricultural systems in the study area.